

Behaviour-Based Quality Assessment of OpenStreetMap Data in Data-Scarce Areas Using Unsupervised Machine Learning

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Despite the widespread use of OpenStreetMap (OSM) data, the quality of OSM data varies considerably across regions and contributors, especially in data-scarce urban areas like Dhaka. Traditional OSM quality assessments rely on extrinsic comparisons with satellite imagery or authoritative datasets, which are often unavailable in the very regions that need the data the most [1], [2]. To overcome this challenge, a reproducible, unsupervised machine learning framework is proposed to assess OSM data quality intrinsically, based on contributor behaviour metadata alone. Specifically, Dhaka—a data-scarce and fast-growing megacity in Bangladesh, selected as a study area—using the hypothesis that distinct contributor behavioural patterns correlate with different levels of data reliability. This behaviour-centric perspective leverages the insight that contributor frequency, recency, thematic focus, and spatial editing behaviour can serve as meaningful proxies for feature quality [3], [4]. Frequent and recent contributions from contributors with a strong thematic focus can assist in achieving higher tagging accuracy and lowering the risk of outdated data. Additionally, contributions that are spatially wide imply systematic, less erratic mapping.

Roads and buildings for Dhaka were extracted from an *.osm.pbf* file using the Pyrosm library. Then an enriched feature vector was created for each unique contributor based on their editing behaviour: *total_edits*, *edit_rate*, *active_days*, *spatial_extent*, *pct_road*, *pct_building*, *weekday_activity*, and *days_since_last_edit*. Temporal activity (frequency and recency), thematic preference (roads vs buildings), and spatial coverage are captured by these features. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) applies for dimensionality reduction and shows that PC1 roughly represents global mapping activity, while PC2 corresponds to thematic attention (road versus building), and PC3 represents the geographical coverage of contributions. These observations are supported by a feature contribution heatmap (Figure 1(a)), which indicates that it is reasonable to consider the behavioural features to be interpretable and highly separable in the component-reduced space. PCA also has the purpose of reducing noise and getting the data ready for clustering [5].

Next, an unsupervised machine learning model was applied in two phases: (1) dimensionality reduction with PCA and (2) clustering with KMeans (4) and HDBSCAN. K-means clustering (with $k = 4$) and HDBSCAN, a density-based clustering, are performed on

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the PCA-transformed feature set. The silhouette score of the K-Means model was 0.951, suggesting high cohesion within the clusters and good separation between the clusters of behaviours. The PCA cluster scatterplot (Figure 1(c)) indicates four separated clusters: (1) Most participants (Figure 1(b)) fall in cluster 0, which mainly encompasses casual or one-hit contributors who probably participate in sporadic mapathons or make large-scale imports, (2) Clusters 1 and 2 consist of moderate to heavy contributors, who are relatively more or less stable, with richer semantic tagging, and whose edits are spatially distributed. (3) Cluster 3 is composed of a small group of “power users”, who are characterised by high activity volume and a large geographical distribution.

HDBSCAN is also used on the same dataset in order to analyse its capability of separating various densities in clusters and noise. HDBSCAN found small, dense clusters and labelled a large percentage of contributors as noise. Although helpful for identifying anomalousness and potential vandalism, HDBSCAN was unable to produce as clear clusters for the main contributors as KMeans, likely because of the extreme imbalance in contributor engagement. This benchmarking demonstrated that K-Means comes with better interpretability and cluster stability and is therefore preferred for behavioural segmentation at the high volumes of the OSM dataset.

To further verify the clustering, the changes in edit volume over time per cluster were investigated, and feature distributions per cluster were calculated. The contributor distribution bar chart (Figure 1 (b)) shows that the participation structure in OSM is highly skewed, which is also in line with previous VGI studies [6, 7]. Feature analysis showed that clusters associated with more recent, frequent, and thematically rich editing were also responsible for higher-quality contributions—consistent with prior work linking contributor experience to data quality [3], [4], [8].

A key contribution of this work is its extensible and repeatable approach. All data processing, feature engineering, PCA and clustering have been performed in Python (Colab) with open-source packages (scikit-learn, geopandas, pyrosm, matplotlib). This method doesn't need any external validation databases, so it is particularly adapted for developing countries and isolated locations, where reference data are limited or unavailable [2].

This study contributes methodologically to three areas in the sciences, more precisely to the area of geospatial data science, unsupervised machine learning, and VGI quality assurance, in showing how user behaviour can be harnessed for deriving inherent data quality. It complements the literature about behaviour-based contributor profiling, incorporates dimensionality reduction to facilitate the interpretation of results, and is an argument against central quality assessment as well as one for local quality assessment, which seems feasible even in urban settings with complex mobility patterns.

Pragmatically, this work can help NGOs, local authorities and the OSM community to support the allocation of resources toward data validation and enrichment where coverage is primarily in lower-quality contribution clusters. It also allows hybrid-quality models with behaviour signals that are augmented with selective extrinsic checks (such as anomaly detection or community verification). For example, contributors from Cluster 3 (power users) may be assigned higher trust weights in quality models, while edits from Cluster 0 may be flagged for further review or enrichment.

In conclusion, a new behaviour-based quality assessment of the OSM report is based on the specific usage of unsupervised machine learning. This cluster- and PCA-driven

design is transparent and interpretable, and completely reproducible. It is a model that addresses the challenges of working in data-scarce urban areas, and it paves the way for behaviour-driven VGI quality models in the framework of urban resilience, infrastructure planning and humanitarian mapping. Future studies will incorporate spatial error measures and use this methodology with longitudinal OSM data for quality evolution monitoring.

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